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Supporting Information

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Ultrafast Humidity Sensing Layers Made by Two-Photon Polymerization and Initiated
Chemical Vapor Deposition

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Ultrafast humidity sensing layers made by two-photon polymerization and initiated chemical vapor deposition

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1 Refractive Index

The measurements were performed with an ellipsometric setup and afterwards the refractive index was calculated from a Cauchy fit model (see equation S1). As samples we used unstructured p(HEMA) thin films on Si-wafers where the result is plotted in figure S1.

$$n(\lambda) = A + \frac{B}{\lambda^2} + \frac{C}{\lambda^4} \quad (\text{S1})$$

Figure S1: Refractive index of a planar p(HEMA) thin film for different humidity values.

2 Simulations

2.1 Hygroscopic swelling

The hygroscopic swelling module calculates the inelastic strain after moisture take up which is proportional to the difference between the concentration and the strain-free reference concentration:

$$\epsilon_{hs} = \beta_h \cdot (C - C_{ref}) \quad (\text{S2})$$

with ϵ_{hs} = inelastic strain, β_h = hygroscopic swelling parameter, C = moisture concentration and C_{ref} = reference moisture concentration

The curve in figure S3 was measured with by in-house ellipsometry that can be combined with a liquid cell to set different controlled humidity levels

for non-crosslinked planar p(HEMA) thin films [30].

2.2 Swelling Curve

For the hygroscopic swelling module experimental data were taken by in-house ellipsometry as shown in fig. S3. For the humidity measurement the ellipsometer can be equipped with a humidity chamber. On the y-axis of fig. S3 d and d_0 describe the actual thickness and initial thickness of a planar thin film layer, respectively.

Figure S2: Measured swelling curve of a planar p(HEMA) thin film. Reproduced with permission from [30].

3 Humidity measurements

The response of the bare 2PP template was tested in the same conditions as reported in the paper for the coated structures. In this case no correlation between the humidity change and the measured signal can be observed.

Figure S3: Humidity measurements made on a 2PP template not coated with the hydrogel